

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART VIII. ON THE INTERNAL FILTER ACTION OF REDUCED TUNGSTIC ACID AND MOLYBDIC ACID SOLS.

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In the previous papers (Parts II, III, IV and V of this series, this Journal, September issue, Vol. XIV) it has been shown that the photo-reduction of sols of tungstic acid and molybdic acid by ultraviolet light of wave-length 366μ with glucose, laevulose, etc. as reductants has the following characteristic features:—

- (1) The velocity of reaction which was followed up to 30% reduction of the photo-active sol, is proportional to the intensity of light absorbed by the reaction mixture, the quantum efficiency being of the order of $0.5 - 1.0$.
- (2) That with excess of reductant, the reaction follows the zero-molecular law, *i.e.*, equal amount of sol is reduced in equal time independent of the ratio of the oxidised and reduced forms of the sol in the system.

It is necessary to mention that these results are obtained only when sufficient precaution has been taken to exclude oxygen from the reaction mixture; otherwise the reduced sol gets re-oxidised by molecular oxygen and erratic velocity constants (sometimes of a unimolecular type) are obtained.

Normally it is to be expected that in such simple systems, the velocity of reaction should be proportional to the light absorbed by the photo-active sol in the higher state of valency, the fraction of the light absorbed by the reduced form of the sol going to waste merely as heat. If the extinction coefficient of the reduced form is of the same order as the original sol, the light absorbed by the photo-active sol will continually become less and less during the progress of the reaction. As a matter of fact, the extinction coefficient of the reduced sol has been found to be much higher than that of the original unreduced sol. A zero-molecular velocity constant is, therefore, contrary to expectation and the problem necessitated a thorough investigation.

As a probable explanation, it was thought that though the reaction mixture did not indicate any turbidity in visible light, the scattering coefficient of the sol for the active ultraviolet radiation may be considerable, and perhaps much larger than that of the reduced sol. With progress in

reaction, the loss due to scattering may be less and compensate for the continuously diminishing light absorption by the active sol. The following experiment (*vide* Fig. 1) was carried out to test this possibility.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Light from the source S, a point-o-lite mercury lamp, is rendered parallel by the lens L, passes through the quartz cell containing 2% CuSO_4 solution in water and through the ultraviolet filter (glass filter No. G 312, *vide* Technological papers of the Bureau of Standards, No. 148) and falls at an angle of 45° upon the quartz cell containing the solution whose scattering power is to be measured. The reflected light is received by the Moll thermopile connected with a very sensitive Moll galvanometer. It was found that the total amount of light scattered by the quartz surface and the solution is about 3% of the total incident light. If the light falls normally upon C (Fig. 1), it will be still less. When reduced sol was taken in C, the amount of light scattered was even somewhat less than 3%. Any explanation of our experimental observation as due to variation in the scattering coefficient, is therefore, impossible.

FIG. 1.

The phenomenon of two dimensional mobility discovered by Volmer (Summary given in *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 359) gave a clue to the proper understanding of the problem. The surface of micelles of tungstic acid sol is initially covered with WO_3 molecules. When such

molecules absorb radiation, they get activated. The unactivated adsorbed molecules are mostly bound to the fixed atoms of the underlying material and can only oscillate around their equilibrium positions. When it absorbs a quantum of radiation, its amplitude of oscillation increases; and if a sufficient part of the radiant energy absorbed is transformed into kinetic energy, the particles will have considerable surface mobility. Under such conditions it does not matter whether light quantum is absorbed by a tungstic acid molecule or a reduced tungstic acid molecule on the micelle surface. For the activated reduced molecule will give its energy of activation by surface collision to a tungstic acid molecule which in its turn will get reduced by reaction with the reductant.

The critical test of such a hypothesis is possible. If for example, it is possible by suitable experimental methods, to bring every molecule of tungstic acid in a micelle to a lower state of valency, then the light absorbed by such a completely reduced micelle will not be available for photochemical reaction. In our photochemical investigation, the micelles of the active sol were not reduced to more than 30% in course of 10 hours; but the complete reduction of a micelle of tungstic acid or molybdic acid can be easily effected either by exposure to sunlight in presence of excess of reductant or by cathodic discharge of hydrogen ions. If such completely reduced sol is now mixed with a reacting system consisting of tungstic acid sol and reductant, taking great care that in the process of mixing,

FIG. 2.

the completely reduced micelles do not get any chance of being partially oxidised by oxygen gas, we would expect that the part of the light

radiations absorbed by the completely reduced micelles will not be available for photoreduction. This has been observed to be the case and a direct proof of the two dimensional mobility of molecules of tungstic acid and molybdic acid on micelle surfaces has thus been obtained.

In Fig. 2 is described the experimental arrangement for the complete cathodic reduction of a sol of tungstic acid, its anaerobic mixing with original sol and reductant and transference of the mixture to the quartz reaction vessel L, which is provided with a long neck and a ground glass joint K with a stop-cock I below the joint.

The flask F contains the tungstic acid sol and had five connections with ground glass joints and water-seals.

(i) Through a three-way stop-cock to vacuum pump, reaction cell and hydrogen generator.

(ii) To H_2 gas outlet tube.

(iii) To Pt electrode.

(iv) To a separating funnel containing a mixture of tungstic acid sol and reductant closed at the top with a rubber stopper holding internally sealed glass tubes for inlet and outlet of hydrogen.

(v) To an agar bridge tube connecting the anode-chamber.

The electrolytic reduction was carried out on a platinum cathode, purified hydrogen gas from a Kipp's apparatus bubbling vigorously through the solution during the electrolysis. When the reduction was completed and the solution cooled to room temperature, the reaction mixture from the separating funnel is poured down under the pressure of H_2 gas above, and thoroughly agitated by the H_2 gas bubbling in F. The mixture was transferred to the reaction vessel with the aid of pump, stop-cock I closed and the vessel taken out from the system by disconnecting the joint at K.

An arrangement similar to the above was also used for complete reduction of the sols in sunlight and subsequent mixing with a definite volume of a mixture of the original sol and reductant and transference to the reaction vessel.

In determining the extinction coefficient, the reduced sol was diluted to the required concentration with air-free redistilled water from the separating funnel.

Measurements of Extinction Coefficient.

TABLE I

 d (thickness of the cell) = 0.5 cm. $\lambda = 366\mu\mu$.

Substance whose extinction coeff. is to be measured.	Conc. of the substance used (c)	Transmission of radiation in ergs/cm ² / sec. through		Ext. coeff. $= \frac{2.3 \log \frac{I_0}{I_d}}{c \cdot d}$
		water in the cell. (I_0)	soln. in the cell. (I_d)	
1. Tungstic acid sol	0.05M	1070	66.7	111
2. Completely reduced tungstic acid sol	0.005	1070	396.3	400
3. Molybdic acid sol	0.05	1373	475.2	43
4. Do	0.05	884.5	297.0	45
5. Completely reduced molybdic acid sol	0.00268	1373	191.5	1450
6. Do	0.000667	1373	812.0	1550

TABLE II.

With tungstic acid sol.

Glucose = 2.5%. $p_H = 1.24$. Temp. = 29.5°. I_{abs} (Intensity of incident radiation in ergs per cm² per sec.) = 1970. $d = 0.5$ cm.

Concentration of sol un-reduced.	completely reduced.	Total I_{abs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (obs.).	I_{abs} by un-reduced sol only.	* $K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (Calc.).
0.05M	0	991	3.49	991	...
0.0475	0.0025M	1017	3.08	862	3.00
0.045	0.005	1036	2.67	743	2.58

* (Calculated taking into account that I_{abs} by the un-reduced sol only is effective.)

TABLE III.

*With molybdic acid sol.*Glucose = 2.5%. Temp. = 29.5°. $\mu_H = 1.73$. $I_{\text{obs}} = 1373$. $d = 0.5$ cm.

Concentration of sol unreduced.	Concentration of sol completely reduced.	Total I_{obs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (obs.).	I_{abs} by un- reduced sol only.	* $K_0 \times 10^{10}$ (Calc.).
0.05M	0	927	2.11	927	...
0.048	0.002M	1261	1.30	539	1.23
0.046	0.004	1346	0.83	343	0.78
0.044	0.006	1373	0.56	251	0.57

We thus see when sol. where the micelles have been completely reduced, is added to the reaction mixture at the beginning of photochemical reaction, the concordance between the calculated and observed values of the velocity constants is only obtained on the assumption that cathodically reduced sol behaves like a pure internal filter.

In our studies of the photochemical reduction of these sols which have been described in the previous papers, the concentration of the reduced sol at the end of the experiment was often greater than 10% of the original sol concentration. Hence if this internal light filter action were operative, the instantaneous velocities of reaction would have diminished continuously until at the end this velocity would have been $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{1}{3}$ rd. of that at the beginning. But in these reactions, the zero-molecular equation was perfectly obeyed during the entire course of the reaction. Hence the explanation holds that so long as unreduced molecules remain in the micelle of a sol, the light quantum absorbed by that micelle is photo-active independently of whether it is absorbed by a molecule of tungstic acid and molybdic acid or their reduced derivatives.

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